

LEADERSHIP DIVERSITY: A TOOL FOR INNOVATIVE AND SUSTAINABLE IMPLEMENTATION OF NATIONAL POLICY ON INCLUSIVE BASIC EDUCATION IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study examined how leadership diversity could be used as a coordinating tool to develop pedagogical principles and practice for innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria. It deploys the mixed studies systematic scoping review method to harness all forms of studies because, from observations, pieces of literature that focus on the subject matter are limited. Available studies obtained were subjected to content analysis through thematic analysis, and results were presented to explain the research objective of this study. It was revealed that ensuring innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria seems low due to the lack of professional teachers and non-availability of development on pedagogical principles and practices that affect the innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria. Therefore, student diversity in the classroom is not catered for in the Nigerian education system. The study concluded that there is a need to effectively develop pedagogical principles and practices to ensure innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria. It recommended the need to review the national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria to meet the diverse learning needs of students in the classroom. There is also the need to retrain teachers in line with the development and provision of several pedagogical principles and practices towards ensuring innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria.

Keywords: Leadership Diversity, Innovative and sustainable, National policy, inclusive basic education, Nigeria

Introduction

Global momentum is channeled towards achieving inclusive education as contained in the Sustainable Development Goals, particularly Goal 4, which is to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and also to promote lifelong learning opportunities for all by the year 2030 (United Nations Development Programme, 2023). This has propelled the need for continuous striving at the local, regional and global levels to ensure everyone has access to education. A fair and inclusive

educational environment is a major correlate for ensuring a fulfilled and healthy classroom and education system in any nation (OECD, 2023).

However, there is poor implementation of the national policy for inclusive basic education in Nigeria as stated by the Federal Ministry of Nigeria (2015) and the National Women Development Centre (2023); Nigerian Online Tribune News (2023); and Centre for the Study of the Economies of Africa (2023). In addition, leadership diversity and

pedagogical principles and practice are major innovative processes important in achieving sustainable implementation of the national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria. This calls for attention, hence, it deems fit to examine the roles leadership diversity and the pedagogical principles and practice could play in the implementation of inclusive basic education in Nigeria. To this end, this article proposes leadership diversity as a coordinating tool to develop pedagogical principles and practice for innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria.

Conceptual Clarification

This section provides the conceptual definition and clarification of various concepts used in this study.

The Concept of Inclusive Basic Education

Inclusive education implies offering quality education for all while respecting diversity and the different needs and abilities, characteristics and learning expectations of the students and communities, eliminating all forms of discrimination” (UNESCO, 2009, OECD, 2024). Also, basic education refers to the type of education that is offered at the primary school up to the junior secondary level, and it’s a nine (9) programme hence, it holds the foundation on which other educational levels in Nigeria’s education system are built upon (Cornelius-Ukpepi & Opuwari, 2019). Its major objective is to eradicate illiteracy, ignorance and poverty, towards the stimulation of personal and national development (Cornelius-Ukpepi & Opuwari, 2019). Therefore, inclusive basic education could be referred to as the process of offering a nine (9) programme education, which cuts across providing quality primary school to junior secondary education for all children, putting into

consideration the social diversity and the different needs and abilities, characteristics and learning expectations of the students and communities, thereby eliminating all forms of discrimination that could hinder access to education in Nigeria. The basic reason for ensuring inclusive basic education is to foster and encourage the inclusion of students with learning disabilities and differences to be independent and to also benefit from the educational resources, practices and activities that are provided for all (Anupriya & Salim, 2014; Shiksha, 2020; OECD, 2024).

However, success in achieving inclusive basic education occurs primarily when the stakeholders of the education system accept, understand, and attend to the differences and diversities in classrooms, putting into consideration the physical, academic, social, cognitive, and emotional state of all students within the education system (McManis, 2017). This could be achieved by first understanding the place of the provision of necessary national policy that could be encompassing and holistic enough to foster the provision and implementation of inclusive basic education for all (OECD, 2023), particularly in Nigeria’s education system.

Inclusive Basic Education in Nigeria

The Federal Ministry of Nigeria (2015) and the National Women Development Centre (2023) noted that the National Policy on Education of Nigeria stipulates that education must be provided for all children and that all children should possess and be given equal rights to qualitative, functional and effective basic education in Nigeria. Also, the Universal Basic Education Act of 2004, as stated by the National Women Development Centre (2023) stipulates that basic education should be provided free and be made mandatory for all school-age children. Therefore, it becomes more challenging to

ensure that in Nigeria, basic education is provided to all children of all ages, from different socio-economic status, and also with different learning abilities, including those with disabilities. Hence, quality education for all is to be ensured while putting into consideration, the social diversity, socio-economic needs and the different children's needs and abilities, characteristics and learning expectations of the students and communities, thereby eliminating all forms of discrimination that could hinder access to quality education in Nigeria as stated by UNESCO (2009) and OECD (2024).

The practices of inclusive education, which also include inclusive basic education in Africa such as Ghana, Uganda, Kenya, and Liberia, among others have attracted attention, while other countries are still reviewing the education system towards inclusive societies (Obi & Ashi, 2016). In developed countries such as the UK, USA, and Canada, among others, education is provided, inculcating the use of specialised strategies and methods for quality dissemination of information and knowledge that cater for all children in the society, including the disabled (Nigerian Online Tribune News, 2023). This form of education allows the neglected child to join the education wagon of other colleagues in the regular classroom hence, a becoming free among counterparts (Nigerian Online Tribune News, 2023).

However, the geometric increase in the number of children who do not have access to quality education in Nigeria, reveals that there is a major problem in the implementation of inclusive basic education in Nigeria (Nigerian Online Tribune News, 2023). Achieving inclusiveness in the education system in Nigeria is still mayhem (Obi & Ashi, 2016; Nigerian Online Tribune News, 2023), as UNICEF (2012) noted that over 10 million children are out of school children. Inclusive education, which in this article

refers to inclusive basic education is still operating in theory and far from practice hence, there is also an issue relating to problems of policy implementation in Nigeria's education system (Sambo & Bwoi, 2015),

According to the Federal Ministry of Education, Nigeria (2015), inclusive education is still combated with several issues hence, challenging its implementation in the Nigerian education system. Also, several vulnerable groups of children do not have access to quality education in Nigeria hence, a high rate of exclusion of certain groups of children that are excluded from access to education in Nigeria (Centre for the Study of the Economies of Africa, 2023). This could have challenged the successful implementation of the national policy for inclusive education in Nigeria hence, Obi & Ashi (2016) noted that there is a need for continuous inquiry and effort on how the nation could achieve effective inclusive education, particularly inclusive basic education in Nigeria.

Leadership Diversity and Pedagogical principles and practice

According to OECD (2024), diversity must be put into consideration in any educational approach or framework that should be proposed for educational inclusion. Hence, inclusive basic education has three guiding principles which are presence; recognition; and relevance (OECD, 2024). The presence relates to access, welcoming and integration of various children with different learning abilities and cultures, coupled with socio-economic differences into the education system. Recognition refers to the visibility, identity and diversities in the society, which in this study could mean leadership diversity. Relevance includes the use of various pedagogical practices, learning styles and contexts to achieve an inclusive education system.

In this article, both leadership diversity and Pedagogical principles and practice are major innovative processes that are viewed to be very important in achieving sustainable implementation of the national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria. Diversity in leadership is a workplace phenomenon that explains the process by which an organization puts into consideration and utilizes different backgrounds, cultures and views of individuals in their leadership process towards achieving organizational set goals (Winston, 2001; Larive, 2023). Leadership diversity focuses on how leaders in an organization aim to achieve organizational goals through the differences, similarities and tensions among groups (Military Leadership Diversity Commission, 2010). Therefore, concerning this paper, leadership diversity could refer to the process by which teachers and administrators in schools aim to achieve educational or classroom goals and objectives by putting into consideration students' differences, similarities and tensions within the classroom, and in the school system, particularly in the learning process. According to OECD (2024), this includes deploying various innovative pedagogical principles and practices that could meet the various and different needs of students in the classroom by the teachers.

Owa (2024) observed that the pedagogy model is concerned with the different methods or strategies teachers use to present knowledge to or teach students in class to achieve better performance and enhance the achievement of educational goals. In recent times, innovative technologies have challenged previous classic ways of teaching and learning to engage students in the classroom (Owa, 2024). Therefore, learning styles and strategies that focus on eliminating monotonous learning and restriction in the classroom and that majorly deploy inclusive teaching approaches give learners

an enhanced classroom experience. According to Cornelius-Ukpepi & Opuwari (2019), national education policies and systems are a good target for the reformation and designing of clear pedagogical strategies that put into consideration the diversities in classrooms towards ensuring innovative and sustainable implementation of inclusive basic education systems in Nigeria.

Literature Review

The National Human Rights Commission (2023) revealed that everyone in Nigeria has the right to education, which implies that everyone is to be included in the teaching and learning process and that everyone should be inculcated into the education system to have a pleasant classroom experience. However, not all in the Nigeria society has this access to quality education, as several individuals could not have access to education in the nation (Oshimade, 2021). Studies such as Eskay, Eskay & Uma (2012) and Oshimade (2021) noted that several factors led to the lack of access to education in Nigeria. These include ignorance, poverty, and bad cultural beliefs, among others. This reveals that inclusive basic education has not achieved success in the Nigerian education system.

Sambo & Bwoi (2015) noted that inclusive education as a concept, implies including all learners in the education system, but could be interpreted differently covering children that are excluded from the education system, based on disability, gender, language, ethnicity, and other factors. UNESCO (2005) defines inclusive education as:

- Recognizing the right to education and providing it in a non-discriminatory system.
- Sharing common vision which also extends to everyone.
- The opinion and acceptance that the school system and other

social places of learning possess the responsibility of educating all the children, coupled with the adults in line with human rights principles.

- Providing continuous process to address and respond to the different needs of everyone and learners, irrespective of the restricted factors which could include disability, gender, age, ethnicity, language, and others. Hence, recognising the fact that everyone can learn.

According to the Federal Ministry of Education (2015), the Nigerian education system has not achieved inclusive basic education because of several issues such as bad classrooms, lack of technology, and laboratories, among others. However, providing access to appropriate education for the socially excluded is a major thrust of inclusive education, a major goal of and a tool for ensuring sustainable development in the nation. The National Policy on Education of Nigeria has stipulated that education must be provided for all children and be given equal rights to qualitative, functional, and effective basic education in Nigeria (Federal Ministry of Nigeria, 2015; National Women Development Centre, 2023). In addition, the Universal Basic Education Act of 2004 affirmed that all school-age children should have access to free and mandatory basic education (National Women Development Centre, 2023).

However, to ensure quality inclusive basic education for all, there is a need to take into consideration the concept and issue of diversity, which in this paper is addressed as leadership diversity to be able to eliminate all forms of discrimination (UNESCO, 2009; OECD, 2024). Also, the concept of diversity, which involves recognizing individual, cultural and socio-economic differences must emphasize the

relevance of using various pedagogical principles and practices that could encourage better teaching and learning styles toward achieving an inclusive basic education system.

Therefore, to achieve innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria, it deems fit to focus on developing pedagogical principles and practices that inculcate the diversity of the society which include putting into consideration the individual, cultural and socio-economic differences of children. Nevertheless, not much is understood in this regard hence, this present article focuses on examining how the recognition of diversity by teachers and school administrators could be used as a coordinating tool to assist in the development of pedagogical principles and practice toward achieving innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria.

Research methods

A mixed studies systematic review was adopted to achieve the objective of the study. The mixed studies systematic review uses several studies that deployed different research designs which include quantitative, qualitative, and review studies, among others. The use of mixed method strategies was adopted to harness all forms of studies that focus on the subject matter of interest. Also, to review the literature relevant to the study, the Cochrane review style, a major reviewing style in the systematic scoping review method was adopted (Sieving, 2007 and Chapman, 2014). Also, the search strategy was informed by the PICOS framework (Richardson, 1995; Huang et al., 2006). The meaning of the acronym is provided below.

P – The Problem or Population
I – The Intervention
C – The Comparison, control or comparator
O – The Outcome(s)

S – The Study type (e.g. quantitative, qualitative, missed, etc)

The PICOS framework used in this study is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. PICOS

	Inclusion	Exclusion	Search terms
Population	Nigeria education system	Other national issues	Sustainable innovative implementation of inclusive basic education in Nigeria, national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria
Intervention	Leadership diversity, pedagogical principles and practice	Other issues in the Nigeria education system	Leadership diversity, pedagogical principles and practice, innovative for inclusive basic education, pedagogical principles and practice for innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria
Comparator Outcome	None Inclusive basic education in Nigeria	None Other national issues	None Inclusive basic education in Nigeria, pedagogical principles and practice for innovative and sustainable implementation of inclusive basic education in Nigeria.
Study type	Mixed studies systematic review	None	Mixed studies systematic review

The initial search process commenced on January 03, 2024, and another search process was repeated on January 13, 2024, to gather relevant information and resources that could cater for the study. Recent information and resources are ensured to be different from the previous ones to eliminate repetition of those covered previously, particularly during the

writing process and reviewing period. In addition, studies that used different studies and methodologies were adopted and considered in this study and materials deployed include those within the years 2015 and 2023. Also, the study deploys the PRISMA Flow Diagram to inform the study search as provided in Figure 1:

Figure 1: The PRISMA Flow Diagram for the Study
 Source: Adeola (2024)

In addition, several components were inculcated in the materials appraisal process, and these cut across the evaluation of the appropriateness of study design used for the materials used in the study, the features of the methodology of the design deployed, the article’s author(s) and sources, among others. Finally, the article deployed data extraction for further synthesis and analysis, and information and materials obtained were subjected to content analysis through thematic analysis, and results were presented to explain the research objective of the study.

Systematic Review of Literature

The study focuses on examining how leadership diversity could be used as a coordinating tool to develop pedagogical principles and practice for innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria. Adeniyi, Josiah & Olojede (2015) examined the determinants of successful inclusive education practice in Lagos State, Nigeria, and adopted a survey research design, focusing on a sample size of 227 teachers and head teachers/principals and data was collected using two inventories which are materials and manpower inventory and attitudinal. Data collected

were subjected to analysis using Pearson moment correlation and multiple regression.

The result of Adeniyi et al. (2015) revealed that the availability of teaching and instructional materials, teaching experience, mindset and the availability and professionalism of the teachers contribute elastically to the success of inclusive education, which in this study implies the success in the implementation and achieving inclusive basic education in Nigeria. This implies that the availability of teaching and instructional materials, teachers' teaching experience, the attitude, coupled with the availability of professional teachers posed a negative significant impact on the success of inclusive basic education in Nigeria. Thus, there is a need for teachers to be able to develop effective pedagogical principles and practices that could cater for the different students in the classroom for innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria.

Oyedeji (2015) examined the lapses in education policy formulation processes in Nigeria and their implications for the standard of education. He identified several lapses that have seriously impeded the education policy formulation processes in Nigeria, which included those related to inclusive basic education. These are the lack of indigenous education policy or the lack of Indigenous inclusive basic education policy, lack of adequate implementation strategy including inclusive basic education in Nigeria, and non-involvement of stakeholders, particularly the teachers. This implied leadership diversity, and not putting into consideration the diversity of students when formulating such policy, the lack of continuity of policy implementation, and lack of political will, particularly to support inclusive basic education in Nigeria. This implies that for a long time, the

implementation of the national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria has not been innovative and sustainable hence, it lacks continuity as the national policy on inclusive basic education is not encompassing to cater for the different needs and the diversity groups of students in the classroom.

Enyiazu (2022) examined the problems of educational policy implementation and its influence on the welfare of the teacher labor market in Nigeria and identified several problems in the implementation of educational policy in Nigeria. These include insufficient funding, lack of accountability in governance, and lack of continuity of education policies, among others. These have, by extension affected the teaching status in Nigeria, due to poor working environment, lack of job satisfaction, leading to teaching ineffectiveness, and the lack of connections between the teachers and the class or school needs, among others. This implies that there is a lack of innovative and sustainable implementation of inclusive basic education in Nigeria.

Idoko (2023) examined the role of teachers in achieving inclusive education in Nigeria and noted that the principles of inclusive education are encapsulated in:

- i. Providing equal opportunity hence, everyone should have equal access to participate in quality education,
- ii. Putting into consideration diversity hence, embracing and celebrating individual and cultural, coupled with the socio-economic differences that exist among the students,
- iii. Actively involving and engaging students, and the stakeholders such as the parents, government, and teachers, among others in the decision-making processes,

- iv. Provision of individualized support which tends to cater to the unique learning needs of every student,
- v. Collaboration which tends to encourage cooperation, particularly among the teachers, parents, and specialists towards the provision of appropriate support,
- vi. Provision of a highly respected and accepted environment that fosters where every individual is treated in the same way and is valued and treated with dignity,
- vii. Place high expectations on individuals by believing in every student's capability,
- viii. Provision of an accessible environment that ensures physical, social, and instructional resource availability for all students.
- ix. Provision of continuous professional development to ensure teachers have the necessary skills and knowledge for the implementation of inclusive practices.
- x. Provision of reflective practice that tends to regularly assess and adapt the teaching strategies that could meet the evolving needs of students.

Also, Idoko (2023) noted that, In Nigeria, teachers play significant roles in ensuring inclusive education, which this study refers to as inclusive basic education by providing a supportive learning environment for all students thereby promoting inclusive education. This is because inclusive education aims at ensuring equal access to education for all students, irrespective of student's abilities, backgrounds, or characteristics. Also, Idoko (2023) highlighted several success stories and best practices in achieving

inclusive education in Nigeria as teachers are filling the position of dedicated and passionate educators, thereby implementing inclusive practices through the adoption of curriculum and provision of individualized support to all students. Also, they foster inclusivity through the creation of a supportive classroom environment where all students have the feeling that they are valued and included in the system. In addition, teachers use different teaching methods and materials to meet the diverse learning needs of every student.

Also, Idoko (2023) revealed that several inclusive teaching strategies are adopted by teachers in Nigeria to meet the diverse learning needs of students. These include the use of different instructional teaching strategies by teachers to cater for the differences and diverse learning needs of all students. This involved the adoption of lesson plans and various instructional materials, and providing additional support where needed for all students. It also involves the modification of curriculum to meet different and diverse learning needs of students to ensure the accessibility of education services for them. This includes the use of alternative assignments, incorporating real-life experience and storytelling, and using inclusive language and images in the different instructional materials that are used.

This implies that, although teachers play a major role in ensuring innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria, the development of pedagogical principles and practices that cater for the differences and diversities of students is paramount to its success. This reveals that the development of pedagogical principles and practice and the ability of teachers to meet diverse needs are important in achieving innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria.

Also, Oke, Samuel & Ezeh (2023) examined how inclusive education could be deployed as a vital tool for improving children with special needs, and revealed that teachers play a significant role in achieving inclusive classrooms for successful inclusive education. The study of Oke et al. (2023) also revealed that inclusive classroom focuses on the provision of equal educational opportunities to all children, which cuts across all categories of children including:

- i. The regular learners: They are typical children referred to as 'normal' or 'regular' children who do not possess any learning challenges but could be of average performance
- ii. The gifted and talented learners: They often do not possess any learning challenge but have few behavioral dispositions that could be contextual and dependent on the gifted child. Hence, when not properly handled, could lead to several issues that could serve as menace to the classroom. These children can achieve self-directed learning, with only minimal instructional guidance, have very high self-expectations, and present high academic performance because of their intellectual creativity.
- iii. The hearing-impaired learners: They are children who do not find it easy to hear any sound and they belong to two major groups which are those who find it hard to hear and the deaf. However, by providing reasonable additional instructional modifications and materials for learning, they could learn just like regular learners. However, some of these hearing-impaired

individuals could be intellectually and creatively gifted.

- iv. The visual impaired learners: These are those individuals finding it difficult to see or could find it difficult to view objects either afar or near. They could be partial-sightedness, long-sightedness, or low vision. However, children with visual impairment problems could learn with additional and reasonable instructional modifications and materials.
- v. Learners having orthopedic learning disabilities: They are learners who possess physical impairments that could affect the use of their hands or legs. These challenges could impede their mobility but do not affect their mental and learning capabilities. Hence, they could compete very effectively with regular children when they have the appropriate learning aids that could assist and enable them to partake in the classroom just like the regular students.
- vi. The learners that have some specific learning disabilities: They are the group of learners that have one or more challenges, particularly in one or more places of their cognitive domain, and could range from dyslexia which is the inability to read, dysgraphia which is the inability to write, the problem of processing and manipulating numbers, among others. Others may also include Attention Deficit Hyperactive Disorder (ADHD), and dyscalculia, among others. In these processes, students may be hyperactive or find it difficult to

- pay attention hence, there could be a need for providing additional learning aids to enhance their performance.
- vii. Those having health impairment: They are learners that have one or more health-related issues, hence, limiting their ability to concentrate or even maintain focus in the teaching and learning process. These health-related issues could be epilepsy, sickle cell, heart disease, cerebral palsy, HIV/AIDS, and others. However, with appropriate accommodation and instructional modification and materials, these sets of students could be helped during the learning process.
- viii. Those individuals that belonged to or have multiple impairments: These are the children who may possess two or more health or handicapping issues thereby affecting the teaching and learning process. However, appropriate instructional modification and materials could assist them in enhancing their performance to an extent.

Emphasizing the work and findings of Oke et al. (2023), it deems fit to re-emphasize that all these different categories of children have different learning needs hence, using the same pedagogical principles and practice for all of them could challenge the innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria. Hence, reaffirming the findings of Idoko (2023) that teachers play significant roles in achieving inclusive education in Nigeria by using differentiating instructional teaching strategies and modifying the curriculum towards meeting the different and diverse

learning needs of students towards ensuring the accessibility of education services for all students.

The Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board (2023), examined the strategic roadmap for inclusive access to quality higher education in Nigeria and revealed that Nigeria is involved in the provision of inclusive education, which includes inclusive basic education, but present practices in inclusive education are not completely consistent with the existing global best practices. This is because the classrooms, laboratories, and others provided for inclusive education in the country do not possess technology that could meet the diverse demands and needs of the different children hence, leadership diversities are not put into consideration. Also, the cognitive domain of the different children is not put into consideration and addressed, particularly for children different from the regular children or students such as the gifted, creative, and talented, those with intellectual deficits, and others. Also, different pedagogical principles and practices such as curriculum compacting, enrichment, bibliotherapy, and others for innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria are not developed for use to cater for the different and diverse kinds of students in the classroom or schools hence, making inclusive education, which in this article refers to inclusive basic education in Nigeria to be deficient in classroom activities and rehabilitation. This implies that leadership diversity is not taken into consideration hence, different pedagogical principles and practices are not inculcated to suit and cater for the diversities of children for better innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria.

Discussion

The article revealed that developing pedagogical principles and practice is very germane for ensuring innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria. The findings revealed that innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria is very poor. This concurs with the findings of UNICEF (2012); Federal Ministry of Education, Nigeria (2015); Obi & Ashi (2016) and Nigerian Online Tribune News (2023) that achieving an inclusive basic education system in Nigeria is still a mayhem and that there is still major issues with policy implementation as stated by Sambo & Bwoi (2015).

If according to Cornelius-Ukpeli & Opuwari (2019), the major objective of inclusive basic education is to eradicate illiteracy, ignorance and poverty, towards the stimulation of personal and national development, it would be necessary to draw attention to the fact that such poor innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria could lead to a higher rate of illiteracy, ignorance, and poverty hence, could create a negative effect on the personal and national development. Thus, this could in extension, create an impediment to the attainment of the Sustainable Development Goals, particularly Goal 4, which is to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and also to promote lifelong learning opportunities for all by the year 2030 as affirmed by the United Nations Development Programme (2023).

Also, in the long run, the Nigerian education system may be lagging in the global momentum channeled towards the need to achieve inclusive education. This could further argue the fact that Nigeria would be lagging in global sustainable educational development because

according to UNICEF (2012); Anupriya & Salim (2014); Shiksha (2020); Nigerian Online Tribune News (2023); Centre for the Study of the Economies of Africa (2023) and OECD (2024), certain percentage of the population of Nigeria are excluded from enjoying the benefits of the provision of educational resources, practices and activities for all.

Also, another major issue that has affected the innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria is the lack of effective development and use of pedagogical principles and practice. The utilization of pedagogical principles and practice in ensuring innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria could be justified by the findings of Oke et al. (2023) who affirmed that there are categories of children which include the regular, gifted & the talented, hearing impaired, visual impaired, learners having orthopedic learning disabilities, learners that have some specific learning disabilities, health impairment learners, and others belonging to or have multiple impairments.

This also supports the works of the OECD (2024) that children and student diversity must be recognized in developing educational approaches or frameworks for inclusive basic education. In addition, the use of different pedagogical principles and practices in the classroom can also be solely achieved by having, training, deploying, and using professional and capable teachers who could deem it fit to place consideration on the diversity of students in the classroom. This could enable the teaching and learning environment to cater for the various diversities of children in the classroom towards achieving innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria. This finding concurs with the work of OECD (2024) that the diversity of

students should be recognized in the classroom through the use of pedagogical principles and practice in achieving inclusive basic education.

Therefore, the use of developing pedagogical principles and practices in achieving innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria could be achievable when there are capable and professional teachers that could use the different pedagogical principles and practices to meet the diverse learning needs of students in classroom and schools. This concurs with the findings of OECD (2024) that recognition of all categories of students in class is paramount, coupled with the relevant use of various pedagogical practices, learning styles, and contexts towards achieving an inclusive basic education system, particularly in Nigeria's education system.

Hence, following the works of Winston (2001) and Larive (2023), there is a need for effective leadership diversity in the classroom in putting into consideration the different backgrounds, cultures, and views of students in their teaching process, particularly in the use of various pedagogical principles and practices towards achieving inclusive basic education in Nigeria. This also supports the findings of Owa (2024) and OECD (2024), that teachers should deploy various innovative pedagogical principles and practices that could meet the various and different needs of students in the classroom hence, eliminating monotonous teaching and learning environments that tend to create restriction in classroom towards giving all learners an enhanced classroom experience.

Recommendations

Several recommendations were made through the findings of this article and they include:

- i. National policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria should be reviewed to meet the diverse learning needs of students in the classroom and in schools which cuts across the regular, gifted & the talented, hearing impaired, visually impaired, learners having orthopedic learning disabilities, learners that have some specific learning disabilities, health impairment learners, and others belonging to or have multiple impairments.
- ii. Classroom diversities, particularly concerning the different students which are the regular, gifted and the talented, hearing impaired, visually impaired, learners having orthopedic learning disabilities, and learners that have some specific learning disabilities, should be put into consideration in the review of the national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria.
- iii. The stakeholders of the Nigerian education system, namely the government, teachers, and policymakers, among others should direct the national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria towards ensuring innovative and sustainable development.
- iv. Developing pedagogical principles and practices towards ensuring innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria should be welcomed.
- v. Grants should be released for progressive research by governments and other national and international NGOs who

deem it fit to support and drive the course of ensuring innovative and sustainable inclusive basic education in Nigeria.

- vi. There should be training for capable and professional teachers in the use of different pedagogical principles and practices to meet the diverse students learning needs in classrooms, and to be able to handle the diversities in the classroom.

Conclusion

The article revealed that ensuring innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria is very poor and studies directed to this objective are very scarce. Also, the need to develop pedagogical principles and practices is germane for ensuring innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria. This could be achievable when there are capable and professional teachers who could use the different pedagogical principles and practices to meet the diverse learning needs of students in the classroom and schools. These include the regular, gifted and talented, hearing impaired, visually impaired, learners having orthopedic learning disabilities, learners that have some specific learning disabilities, health impairment learners, and others belonging to or have multiple impairments.

However, the lack of professional teachers and the lack of the availability and deployment of pedagogical principles and practice tend to affect and limit the innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria hence, students' diversities in the classroom is not catered for in the Nigeria education system.

However, the use of different pedagogical principles and practices in the classroom by professional and capable teachers could enable the teaching and learning environment that would cater for the various diversities of children in the classroom towards achieving innovative and sustainable implementation of national policy on inclusive basic education in Nigeria.

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